

Assignment 1: Science Investigation Report

By Simon Sez

Aim:

To look at the germination of grass seeds and the different conditions that affect growing

Hypothesis:

Grass seeds like warmth and light. I think that the grass seeds that grow the tallest will be the ones that grow in optimum conditions.

Materials:

1. Two types of grass seed
2. Planting containers

Method:

1. Put 2 grass seeds in each of the containers. One container has soil, one container has a cloth, one container has cotton wool.
2. Water the seeds in each of the containers.
3. Put the seeds in soil outside.
4. Put the seeds in wool on the window sill
5. Put the seeds in cloth in the laundry cupboard
6. Water the seeds on the window sill each day do stop the seeds drying out
7. Measure how tall the seedlings have sprouted for the next 28 days

Results:

1. **Soil:** the tallest seedling was 5 cm and the seeds all sprouted looking good.
2. **Cotton wool:** the tallest seedling was 2 cm and the seeds mostly sprouted but some were a bit mouldy
3. **Cloth:** the tallest seedling 0cm as none of the seeds sprouted.

Conclusion:

Obviously the seeds that sprouted best were the ones in the soil which is what I expected. The soil must contain other nutrients to feed the seedlings as they grew best.

This was a fun experiment and I might get my students to do the same experiment next term.

The Nature of Science strand topics from the curriculum are:

Understanding about Science: Identify ways in which scientists work together and provide evidence to support their ideas.

Understanding about Science: Appreciate that science is a way of explaining the world and that science knowledge changes over time.

Communicating in Science: Begin to use a range of scientific symbols, conventions, and vocabulary.

Success criteria... what mark should Simon Sez be awarded?

Henry David Thoreau bemoaned people's blindness to significant phenomena: "The question is not what you look at, but what you see."

Criteria	Not answered 0	Very poor 1	Poor 2	Satisfactory 3	Good 4	Excellent 5
1. An authentic and non-trivial topic suitable for scientific investigation has been identified and the stimulus for that topic has been explained. An explanation of aspects of the Nature of Science as it applies to the investigation is explained in an appropriate context.	If topic not suitable or trivial, automatic fail, student must resubmit. Must be more than following recipe or procedure (eg, from web)	Suitable topic identified and stimulus explained & linked to, eg, being fun, gaining skills or confidence, solving a problem (in depth).	Suitable topic identified and stimulus explained & linked to, eg, being fun, gaining skills or confidence, solving a problem (in depth). AND One of the NoS aspects of the investigation is explained in an appropriate context	Suitable topic identified and stimulus explained & linked to, eg, being fun, gaining skills or confidence, solving a problem (in depth). AND Two of the NoS aspects of the investigation are explained in an appropriate context	Suitable topic identified and stimulus explained & linked to, eg, being fun, gaining skills or confidence, solving a problem (in depth). AND Three of the NoS aspects of the investigation are explained in an appropriate context	Suitable topic identified & linked to, eg, being fun, gaining skills or confidence, solving a problem (in depth). AND More than three of the NoS aspects of the investigation are explained in an appropriate context
2. Enjoyable experiences of science have been described (either as emerging from or contrasting with aspects of the documented investigation) and characteristics of enjoyable science explained.	If enjoyable or otherwise experiences have not been discussed in depth, automatic fail, student must resubmit	1 enjoyable experience identified in depth contrasted / compared to prior experiences AND 1 enjoyable characteristic linked to motivating learning discussed in depth.	1 enjoyable experience identified in depth contrasted / compared to prior experiences AND 2 enjoyable characteristic linked to motivating learning discussed in depth	2 enjoyable experience identified in depth contrasted / compared to prior experiences AND 2 enjoyable characteristic linked to motivating learning discussed in depth.	3 enjoyable experience identified in depth contrasted / compared to prior experiences AND 3 enjoyable characteristic linked to motivating learning discussed in depth	More than 3 enjoyable experience identified in depth contrasted / compared to prior experiences AND More than 3 enjoyable characteristic linked to motivating learning discussed in depth.
3. Opportunities for further investigations which would advance knowledge in this field have been discussed with reference to the Nature of Science strand	If opportunities for further investigations are not made with reference to specific Science aims/ objectives, automatic fail, student must resubmit. Lists / bullet points instead of discussion also fail	1 opportunity described in depth with reference to specific aims and/or objectives AND 2 or more opportunities described in depth without reference to specific aims and/or objectives	2 opportunities described in depth with reference to specific aims and/or objectives (must be in connection with collecting more data)	3 opportunities described in depth with reference to specific aims and/or objectives (must be in connection with collecting more data)	4 opportunities described in depth with reference to specific aims and/or objectives (must be in connection with collecting more data)	5 or more opportunities described in depth with reference to specific aims and/or objectives (must be in connection with collecting more data)
4. Journal has appropriate structure and headings as a 'science journal' describing a scientific method of investigation which is appropriate to the topic and conducted in accordance with scientific conventions and utilises relevant equipment	If journal is incomplete or lacking in detail, automatic fail, student must resubmit. Could use typical lab report layout but also other headings to address other criteria, eg, "enjoyable experiences"	No headings but has structure AND Discusses all steps in the method(s) used but lacking specific details relevant for another person to reproduce AND utilises equipment from home or school	Headings & structure AND Discusses all steps in the method(s) used but lacking specific details relevant for another person to reproduce AND utilises equipment from home or school	Headings & structure AND Discusses all steps in the method(s) used and in enough depth for another person to reproduce AND utilises equipment from home or school	Meets SATISFACTORY AND describes steps or procedures in specific detail, eg particular brand of reagent, care with handling organisms or apparatus, etc. (<i>does not matter if no duplicate samples or does not repeat experiment</i>)	Meets GOOD AND Method includes techniques to reduce experimental error or calibrate observations/data (eg, <i>determine scale of microscopic images, use of keys to identify organisms, minerals</i>)
5. Appropriate data is collected, numerical transformations are applied if appropriate, and representations of data gathered are suitable to the topic and nature of the data	If representations of data is lacking or no appropriate raw data, eg, in tables, automatic fail, student must resubmit	Inappropriate method used so data is not valid or appropriate (eg, failing to collect multiple samples or failing to carry out multiple trials, if they were appropriate) OR Numerical transformations are inappropriate (eg, <i>incorrect use of graph, average values or %</i>)	Appropriate method used so data is valid and appropriate (including collecting multiple samples or carrying out multiple trials, if they were appropriate) AND Representations of data are not appropriate (eg, incorrect use of raw data table, incorrect encoding [recording] of measurements / observations)	Valid / appropriate data recorded (including collecting multiple samples or carrying out multiple trials, if they were appropriate) AND Representations are appropriate (eg, raw data table, observational drawing) AND Numerical transformations & representations are appropriate (eg, <i>magnification factor, line graph, pie chart, %</i>)	Meets SATISFACTORY AND Multiple measurements used to reduce error, (<i>or other strategy</i>) OR Indication of scale and magnification factor for images of organisms OR Model described in detail (eg, <i>time lapse, flowchart, other visual tool</i>)	Meets GOOD AND Estimation of accuracy of data collected (eg, <i>error bars on graphs or +/- %</i>). <i>Error bars must be calculated in an appropriate way, not just inserted automatically by Excel wizard</i>)
6. Logical conclusions (findings) have been drawn with reference to the data collected	If conclusion does not refer to data collected to support the conclusion, automatic fail, student must resubmit	Conclusion stated using data collected to support conclusion, but incorrect interpretation of data or incorrect conclusion from data	Conclusion stated using data collected to support conclusion, but not enough data collected or data not processed appropriately to be confident about conclusion	Appropriate conclusion using data collected to support conclusion [<i>even if method flawed</i>] (eg, finding a pattern or trend; identifying organisms from a survey; carrying out a Fair Test; testing the functioning of a piece of equipment or a new procedure)	Meets SATISFACTORY AND Suggesting sources (<i>more than one</i>) of error or identifying the limitations of the method/data to support the conclusions OR Suggestions (<i>more than one</i>) for improving experimental design	Meets GOOD AND Suggesting sources of error or identifying the limitations (<i>more than one</i>) of the method/data to support the conclusions AND Suggestions (<i>more than one</i>) for improving experimental design

In terms of the marking rubric I hope the following will be useful:

Criteria 1 – 3 could be considered the summary of the process; what was done, what was enjoyable (or not enjoyable!), where to next; the focus is on **science education**.

Criteria 4 - 6 are the scientific methods used; the focus on **working like a scientist**.

Criteria 1 is about your rationale for your topic – what was it you were investigating and why is this an authentic experience for you? A true investigation or experiment is one where you do NOT know the outcome ahead of time. Avoid following simple procedures or recipes from “science” websites like Steve Spangler, they are nothing more than simple demonstrations. Instead, your investigation should enable taking time to look at the world around you; prior knowledge is NOT needed! There is also an opportunity to show you understand the strategies scientists use to investigate; pick a **different** strategy each time so by 76305 you are confident with practical work. Do chemists work the same way as biologists or physicists? This is your time to find this out.

This is where you can link to the Nature of Science; how will you experience being a citizen scientist by DOING authentic science? This is why the NoS Aims come first in the curriculum, these aims are a way to live and think (first) to gain knowledge (second). Please quote the actual wording from the curriculum, there was a link to this in module 1. For example, you could discuss in what ways this investigation illustrates aspects of “Communicating in Science” with a specific Level 5 objective listed. You need to discuss a number of these according to the marking rubric. This must be a discussion in paragraphs. Single sentences are not considered ‘in depth’ at this level of study

Criteria 2 is about one of the important learning outcomes for this course; that science can be enjoyable and FUN...**but not in a trivial way**; ‘enjoyable’ here means something that motivates you to stay engaged in the activity. Be careful that you understand this is about non-trivial experiences that motivate and enhance learning. **What specifically drives people to put time and energy into something unfamiliar and challenging?**

It is not enough to say eg, counting was “exhilarating” or measuring was “mind-blowing”. Sufficient time needs to be spent reflecting in some depth about WHAT you think are fun / rewarding / enjoyable / motivating experiences, WHERE in the investigation did these types of experiences occur, and explain WHY they were enjoyable.

Alternatively, what was NOT enjoyable or frustrating? We don't mind if you found nothing enjoyable; some of your students may not find science enjoyable, but these investigations encourage you to reflect on WHY this might be to prepare for the lessons you will plan and teach in 76305.

If we wish to make our lessons enjoyable, and not in a trivial way, we need to be able to reflect on this and communicate our thinking about this to others. There is a **brief** example for ONE experience in the critique of Simons report further on (point 2). Notice that bullet points are not appropriate in discussions and explanations. This must be a discussion in paragraphs. Single sentences are not considered ‘in depth’ at this level of study.

Criteria 3 is about the next steps; activities or investigations that permit collecting more observations or data AFTER your current investigation has finished. What other questions arose? This is why the NoS Aims come first in the curriculum, these aims are a way to live and think (first) to gain knowledge (second). Please quote the actual wording from the curriculum, there was a link to this in module 1. For example, you could discuss how making changes to your method illustrates aspects of “Understanding about Science” with a specific Level 5 objective listed. Take some time considering this before you write. This must be a discussion in paragraphs. Single sentences are not considered ‘in depth’ at this level of study.

Criteria 4 is about the method and reproducibility of your project. This must be clearly described in enough detail, perhaps as a list of numbered steps, so that another person can decide if your data collection is valid, and hence if your conclusions are valid. It also enables another person to try and replicate your results.

Criteria 5, not surprisingly, is about the numbers. Always consider what you will be **measuring** or **counting** when planning your investigation...this is your raw data that you will analyse later using some sort of statistical analysis or visual tool (a chart or graph). Criteria 5 includes your raw data, but also your processed data, and by using numbers, indicating how the results might be interpreted. We can also talk about proportions or percentages, and we can think about how a large number of samples provide more confidence that our conclusions are valid. A conclusion based on measurements of food preferences of birds based on just two observations, or over just two days, is LESS reliable than one based on 20 or more observations over a longer period.

Criteria 6 requires a conclusion supported by referring to the numbers/graphs/equations you have generated as you process the raw data collected. How confident can you be that your conclusion is reasonable with regards to the original question? What could you improve in your methods used?

Hot tips:

- Abandon any notion of a High School science report or under-grad lab reports. This is **real science!** You won't have a hypothesis if your strategy for investigating in science does not require one. Why worry about variables? Are you doing a Fair Test? Make sure you engage with Module 1 to learn about the different strategies scientists use when investigating, and try to avoid Fair Testing which is over-represented as a 'method'. Fair Testing is quite limited, often to consumer testing activities, while the other strategies are used far more often.
- Keep it simple, take time out to really look at the world and notice something **in particular**. Leave your assumptions behind and understand **reading is NOT research**. Don't get worried about variables...why do you think you need to? Look at the world, really look, and see what catches your attention as odd, interesting, or worrying! What will you do? Survey? Build a piece of home-made equipment to use? Learn a new practical skill? Learn a new maths skill?
- All science involves noticing size, shape, proportion, weight, speed, height, direction, amount, etc. **There is always something to count to measure using numbers**. Even if doing an observational drawing, you will need to include the scale of the image compared to the actual object. Science is a great way to teach maths!
- Be clear about what 'raw data' is and 'processed data' is; the last chapter of Module 1 has some help here. Always carry out any trials **at least twice** otherwise your conclusion is unreliable. **Seeing something once is not enough to claim a pattern or a trend**.
- A model is not a toy, miniature, or replica of something. In science a model is a **working simulation of a process**. The model enables you to take measurements (collect data) which then MUST be compared to the real-life situation to see if the model is a close approximation of reality. Think wind tunnels for developing new body shapes for cars (to reduce air friction) or how the evening weather forecasts are generated (using climate models in a super computer). If you made a working model heart you must compare its functioning (using data) to a real heart.
- Try something different each time. You have four opportunities in 76301 – 76304 to experience authentic science. Will you focus this time on your numeracy skills, interpreting data or using equipment? Will you move away from Fair Testing and try creating a simulation or working model of a process in science and compare measurements of the model with measurements in the real world? (models in science are not cardboard or clay representations remember!)
- Keep in mind we are preparing you for 76305 where you will plan and teach your own mini-unit of work; put yourself in your students shoes...what are the boring or repetitive bits of science? Rather than being seen as boring, do some tasks just require patience and being methodical? What are the enjoyable or creative or motivating aspects of science investigations? Does using science help make the learning more applied and relevant? Could you use dual assessment to do one activity but assess both numeracy AND science? The PPDAC cycle in maths and traditional scientific method look very similar!

Have fun, prior knowledge is **not** needed when you look at something new and genuinely interesting...

There have been many great investigations done by Primary teachers, surpassing anything done in High School...because they engaged with Module 1 and became amateur scientists...will you?

Suggestions for improvement...but let's look at what was asked...

Task

In regular entries, record the process of planning, conducting and reporting the outcomes of an investigation. Reflect on how much you enjoyed this experience compared to some of the other biology learning you have experienced. Identify the characteristics that make a biology learning experience more enjoyable or less enjoyable for you.

Purpose

This task is used to assess two learning outcomes for this course:

1. Narrate enjoyable experiences of doing biology and explain what made them enjoyable.
2. Plan, conduct and report on a small scale scientific investigation utilizing relevant biology concepts, knowledge, facilities and equipment.

Having a clear idea of what makes this area of science more enjoyable or less enjoyable will have an impact later on how you design biology related experiences for students. Similarly, you will find it easier to help students conduct different elements of science investigations if you have a clear personal understanding of the full process.

Simon has not kept a learning journal so he has not made any comments from this about what he did or reflections of what he was thinking during the process. It is not the science that makes this a Level 7 course but the reflections and critical thinking.

1. He has not said why he thought growing seeds would be enjoyable, motivating or fun. Why pick a topic you already know the outcome of? One of the important learning outcomes for this course is that maths as a science can be enjoyable and FUN...**but not in a trivial way**; 'enjoyable' here means something that motivates you to stay engaged in the activity!
2. Simon could identify or list WHAT people think are fun experiences, WHERE in his investigation did the types of enjoyable experiences listed occur, and explain WHY they were enjoyable. For example

*"Students often enjoy problem solving. This is because they get to take as much time as they need to solve the challenge and they enjoy tasks that have real consequences for **them**. My investigation involved problem solving too; working out how to keep the cat from knocking over the plants, working out where to measure the height from, and making an automated watering system. I most enjoyed keeping the cat out of the plants as it was a chance to observe the plants in peace and quiet and forget about work."*

This **brief** example discusses ONE worthwhile experience (a characteristic, a description & explanation).

3. Simon has changed far too many variables (factors) in his experiment. If he was interested in in what conditions affect growth rate, he should have changed ONE condition, eg, the amount of water in the three containers, but placed the containers in the same location, at the same temperature, in the same substrate (soil, cloth or cotton wool) for the same period of time. For help with fair tests, see <http://nexusresearchgroup.com/fun-science/fair-test.htm>

I make a list of variables (eg, light, water, temperature, etc) putting one at a time on post-it notes. I select one post-it note variable as 'the condition we will change', and put the rest of the variables on the post-it notes into 'all these other conditions we will keep the same' box.

4. Simon's conclusion is invalid because he cannot say which one or combination of environmental factors actually promoted faster seedling growth.
5. Simon's conclusion is invalid because he forgot that the seed is a food store for the plant (embryo) inside the seed. Once the first leaf appears, the seedling will manufacture its own food via photosynthesis. It is a common misunderstanding that plants get food from soil.

6. Spelling and setting out (typos) needed editing. His font size is too big (please use 10 or 12 font)
7. Simon could have planted more than two seeds per container, as some seeds may have been dead or damaged during the packaging process. 6 or 8 may be reasonable depending on the container size. This is a maths course after all. **Seeing something once is not enough to claim there is a pattern or trend in the data! You must repeat any trials at least twice and calculate an average.**
8. A table of results could have been kept where the height of each seedling is recorded individually and then the average height for the container is calculated. This 'evens out' or minimises the impact of any individual seedling that grows in an unusual or atypical fashion. This table is called 'raw data'.
9. For valid conclusions to be drawn, the raw data is processed further. Simon could have presented his data as a bar chart, displaying the average height of seedlings over the 28 day period for each of the three different treatments. He would realise he had changed too many conditions at once when he came to relating seedling height to....the presence of cotton wool? Or cloth? Or sunlight? Or water?
10. Simon has not suggested any further work he could do to learn about plants that is linked to the specific NoS Aims and Objectives. Make sure you have read these (a link is provided in Module 1). He has just listed the aims, not discussed or reflected on them. He should avoid using lists or bullet points when he was asked to discuss and explain; this requires paragraphs (and more than one or two sentences at this level of study).
11. There is a 3500 word limit...at only 240 words, Simon had space to go into more detail.
12. This experiment followed a Fair Test methodology. Research show that schools focus too much on Fair Testing while research scientists commonly engage in **other types** of investigation;

- Click on a link
you wish to
open...
- [Strategies for investigating biology](#)
 - [Strategies for investigating chemistry](#)
 - [Strategies for investigating physics](#)
 - [Strategies for investigating geology and astronomy](#)

For example, Simon may have felt more confident building a simple soil moisture tester and surveying his home or school grounds. He may have enjoyed the combination of science, technology and measurement.

13. There is a **list of equipment** AND suggestions for investigations available from the first chapter of Module 1 *Being a Scientist*;

The *Orientation* module describes **keeping a reflective learning journal** that may be useful for collating evidence that can be used in your report.

Simon's example report above is for you to get familiar with the marking rubric. There is no single 'best' or correct or 'good' example of a report to provide you with; there are many different ways of putting the report together depending on the type of investigation strategy you use.

If you take note of the guidance in the course and the discussions here you should be fine!